

2-MERCAPTO-3-SUBSTITUTED PHENYLQUINAZOL-4-ONES

BY G. R. DAVE, G. S. MEWADA AND G. C. AMJIN

The quinazolone derivatives, studied by several workers (Baker *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, 18, 78; Bami and Dhatt, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1957, 16B, 558; 1959, 18C, 256; Sen and Singh, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 787, 807 *et seq*), are recently receiving more attention as potential antimalarials. Only a few quinazolone derivatives are, however, known containing sulphur atom in the molecule (Elderfield, "Heterocyclic Compounds", John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, Vol. VI, 1956, p.369). 2-Mercapto-3-phenyl- and -3-tolyl-quinazol-4-ones have been described in literature (McCoy, *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 1688; Pawlewski, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 131; Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1930, 7, 981). In the present communication several 2-mercapto-3-substituted phenylquinazol-4-ones have been synthesised by two general methods outlined below. The compounds are listed in Table I.

(i). A mixture of 2-aminobenzoic acid (II, 1 M) and monosubstituted thiourea (1 M) was heated at 180-90° for about 2 hours, keeping a long tube as condenser. On cooling, the reaction mass was treated with water, followed by a 10% NaOH solution. The alkaline solution was filtered, and the filtrate acidified with HCl, when 2-mercapto-3-substituted phenylquinazol-4-ones (I) separated.

(ii). A solution of 2-aminobenzoic acid (II, 1 M) and aryl isothiocyanate (1 M) in sufficient quantity of ethanol was refluxed on a water bath for about 1½ hrs. The product, separating on cooling and dilution, was extracted with alkali. 2-Mercapto derivative was obtained as in (i).

TABLE I

(I: X=).	M. P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Calc.
2-OMe	253°	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.94	11.26
4-OMe	284°	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	11.03	11.26
2-Cl	268°	C ₁₄ H ₈ ON ₂ ClS	10.81	11.09
3-Cl	291°	C ₁₄ H ₈ ON ₂ ClS	10.78	11.09
4-Cl	253°	C ₁₄ H ₈ ON ₂ ClS	11.03	11.09
2-NO ₂	234°	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.31	10.70
3-NO ₂	262°	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.43	10.70
4-NO ₂	287°	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.55	10.70
2-COOH	288°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₂ S	10.43	10.74
4-SO ₃ H	291°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂	18.93	19.17

All the compounds were crystallised from acetone as colorless plates, after treatment with charcoal.

The preparation of the other Bz-substituted quinazolones and study of the reactivity of these compounds are under progress.

Authors thank Dr. S. R. Patel, Chemistry Department, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad-9, for kind interest in the work.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
M. R. SCIENCE INSTITUTE,
GUJARAT COLLEGE, AHMEDABAD-6.,

AND

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
M. N. COLLEGE,
VISNAGAR (NORTH GUJARAT).

Received February 19, 1960.